

ABSTRACT

This study aimed to assess and determine the Level of Compliance to the Expanded Program of Immunization in Barangay Anolid, Mangaldan, Pangasinan.

Along with this, this study also aimed to answer the questions: Are Health Care Facilities and Personnel available in the barangay?; What is the current Immunization Status of Children 0-5 years old in the community?; Is there a significant relationship between the Level of Compliance to the Expanded Program on Immunization (EPI) and the Degree of Knowledge of mothers in the barangay about the vaccines included in the program?; and, What are the reasons for compliance and non-compliance to the EPI in the community?

This study used the descriptive method of research which employed the questionnaire and records analysis techniques of gathering data, as the study focused on the EPI implementation in the above-stated barangay. The study identified the Level of Compliance to the EPI in Barangay Anolid. It also involved a thorough analysis and interpretation of data gathered.

The study was primarily focused on the different variables and factors that affect the Level of Compliance to the EPI in the community like the Availability of Health Care Facilities and Personnel and the Level of Knowledge of Mothers/ Parents/ Guardians regarding the EPI vaccines.

The researchers conclude that there is a High Level of Compliance to the Expanded Program on Immunization in Barangay. Majority of the subject-cases, children 0-5 years old, received different vaccines appropriate to their age, that is, even though, there are still cases of non-compliance and non-completion of vaccine due to some reasons stated such as Lack of Income and Distance to the Barangay Health Center.

In order to improve and develop the Level of Compliance and implementation of the EPI in the community, the researchers recommend that BHCs and other related Health Care Facilities should apply various techniques and method like Information Drives/ Campaigns for them to efficiently implement the program. Ties to NGOs and other abled members of the society should be further established to minimize the hindrances in the implementation of the program.